

MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN AGRICULTURE AND FARMING

¹Guzal Eshchanova, ²Dilbar Usmonova, ³Nigora Yokubova

¹“Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers” National Research University, associate professor

^{2,3}“Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers” National Research University, Teachers

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10939801>

Abstract. *In the given article the advancement, which is more imperative in a modern farming than ever some time recently and the industry as a entire is confronting gigantic challenges from rising costs of supplies and labor deficiencies to changes in customer inclinations for straightforwardness and supportability are presented.*

Keywords: *modern agriculture, innovative technologies in agriculture, advanced farming, advancement, advanced farming, confronting gigantic challenges, labor deficiencies, changes in customer inclinations.*

There's expanding acknowledgment from farming organizations that prompt arrangements are required for these challenges. Indoor vertical cultivating can increment trim yields, overcome constrained arrive region, and indeed decrease farming's affect on the environment by cutting down the remove traveled within the supply chain. This unused concept can be characterized as the hone of developing create stacked one over another in a closed and controlled environment. Its key trait is that it can essentially decrease the sum of arrive space required to develop plants compared to conventional cultivating strategies. Vertical agribusiness has the included esteem that in a few setups it doesn't require soil for plants to develop. Most are either hydroponic -the plants develop in a nutrient-dense bowl of water, or aeroponic, where the plant roots are efficiently showered with water and supplements. The conventional animals industry could be a division that's seemingly the foremost imperative however broadly ignored segment, because it gives much-needed renewable characteristic assets that we depend on each day.

Customarily known as running the commerce of farms, cattle farms, and other related agribusinesses, animals administration includes keeping up exact monetary records, overseeing laborers, and guaranteeing the correct care and bolstering of creatures. In any case, mechanical progressions in agribusiness are revolutionizing the world of creature cultivation. These improvements have significantly made strides the industry, making the following and overseeing of animals much simpler and speedier. Animals innovation can upgrade the efficiency, welfare, and administration of creatures and animals. The “connected cow” concept is the result of preparing groups with sensors to screen their wellbeing and increment efficiency. By joining person wearable sensors to dairy animals, makers can keep track of day by day action and health-related issues and make operational choices rapidly and effortlessly.

Creature genomics may be a unused sort of horticulture innovation that can be characterized as the ponder of the whole quality scene of a living creature and how its interaction with others can impact the animal's development and improvement. Genomics helps livestock producers get it the hereditary chance of their crowds and decide the long run productivity of their animals. So, by being key with creature determination and breeding choices, makers can optimize the productivity and yields of animals crowds. Agtech has gigantic benefits for the industry. Data-driven decision-making leads to superior and more proficient choices that will make strides the efficiency of animals crowds. In later decades, the nursery industry has changed from little offices utilized basically for investigate and tasteful purposes (botanic gardens) to much bigger offices that compete specifically with land-based routine nourishment generation.

Nowadays, in huge portion due to the huge later enhancements in developing innovation, the industry is seeing a blooming like no time some time recently. Nurseries are progressively rising that are large-scale, capital-infused, and urban-centered. Nourishment traceability has been at the center of later nourishment security discourses, especially with unused headways in blockchain applications. Due to the nature of perishable nourishment, the nourishment industry is greatly helpless to making botches that would eventually influence human lives. Blockchain can be utilized to unravel critical issues such as nourishment extortion, security reviews, supply chain inefficiency, and nourishment traceability within the current nourishment framework.

Traceability is basic for the nourishment supply chain. The current communication system inside the nourishment environment makes traceability a time-consuming errand, since a few parties are still following data on paper. The blockchain structure guarantees that information focuses can be produced and shared safely by all parties along the nourishment esteem chain, an responsible and traceable framework

As the exhibit has created definitely, it has additionally experienced clear designs in afterward a long time. Progressed nurseries are getting to be continuously tech-heavy, utilizing Driven lights and computerized control systems to immaculately tailor the creating environment. Productive nursery companies are scaling inside and out and finding their creating workplaces near urban center focuses to capitalize on the ever-increasing request for neighborhood food. To attain these deeds, the nursery industry is getting to be continuously capital-infused, utilizing meander financing and other sources to build out the establishment to compete inside the current exhibit. Cultivation is encountering an progression - development is getting to be an imperative parcel of each commercial develop. Unused exactness cultivation companies are making progresses that allow farmers to maximize yields by controlling each variable of trim developing such as moistness levels, soil conditions, and microclimates. By giving more exact methodologies for planting and creating crops, precision agribusiness engages agriculturists to amplify efficiency and manage costs.

Traceability is basic for the nourishment supply chain. The current communication system inside the nourishment biological system makes traceability a time-consuming assignment, since a few parties are still following data on paper. The blockchain structure guarantees that information focuses can be created and shared safely by all parties along the nourishment esteem chain, an responsible and traceable framework. Endless information focuses with restrictive names can be recorded instantly without alteration. The utilize cases of blockchain in nourishment go past guaranteeing nourishment security. It also adds esteem to the current showcase by building up a record within the organize and adjusting advertise estimating. The conventional cost component for buying and offering depends on the judgments of the included players, instead of the data given by the whole esteem chain. Giving get to to information would make a all encompassing picture of supply and request, a commercial center with gigantic straightforwardness. Blockchain can be utilized to unravel critical issues such as nourishment extortion, security reviews, supply chain inefficiency, and nourishment traceability within the current nourishment framework. Tremendous information focuses with restrictive names can be recorded quickly without adjustment. As a result, a record of nourishment development from cultivate to table can be checked in real-time.

The conventional animals industry may be a segment that's broadly neglected and under-serviced, in spite of the fact that it is apparently the foremost imperative. Livestock provides much-needed renewable common assets that we depend on day by day. The financial matters of the animals industry shifts from season to season, meaning it's not continuously beneficial. With less ventures comes fewer adoptions of innovation. Animals administration is customarily known as running the trade of poultry ranches, dairy ranches, cattle farms, or other livestock-related agribusinesses. Animals supervisors must keep precise monetary records, oversee specialists, and guarantee legitimate care and nourishing of creatures. Later patterns have demonstrated that innovation is revolutionizing the world of animals administration. Modern advancements within the past eight to ten a long time have significantly

progressed the industry, making following and overseeing animals much less demanding and more data-driven. This innovation can come from dietary advances, hereditary qualities, and advanced innovation. Animals cultivating mechanical companies are creating sensors to screen real-time drain generation and quality, wellbeing, and pregnancy hormones. In expansion, virtual wall can move creatures wearing a sensor remotely from one range of a field to another. Indeed mechanical technology is progressing quick in this industry, tending to the challenges of labor deficiencies on conventional animals ranches.

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